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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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SYMPTOMS, CAUSES AND TREATMENTS FOR SHOULDER INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to pathologies associated with shoulder joint injuries in rowers and kayakers. Today, shoulder joint injuries are one of the most common pathologies among injuries of large joints, and the possibility of the occurrence of this pathology in the literature has been studied by scientists from European countries, the Commonwealth and our Republic.

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СИМПТОМЫ, ПРИЧИНЫ И МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЙ ПЛЕЧА (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена патологиям, связанным с травмами плечевого сустава у гребцов и байдарочников. На сегодняшний день травмы плечевого сустава являются одной из самых распространенных патологий среди травм крупных суставов, а возможность возникновения данной патологии в литературе изучалась учеными стран Европы, Содружества и нашей Республики.

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YELKANING SHIKASTLANISHINING BELGILARI, SABABLARI VA DAVOLASH USULLARI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola kanoe va baydardada eshkak eshuvchilarning yelka bo'g'imining shikastlanishlari bog'liq bo'lgan patologik holatlarga bag'ishlangandir. Hozirgi kunda yelka bo'g'imining shikastlanishi katta bo'g'imlar shikastlanishi orasida uchraydigan eng keng tarqalgan patologiyalaridan biri bo'lib, yevropa, hamdo'stlik mamlakatlari va respublikamiz olimlari tomonidan olib borilgan ishlarning adabiyotlarda ushbu patologik holatning paydo bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan holatlar o'rganilgan.

Shoulder joint injury is one of the most common pathologies of large joints and accounts for 16 to 55% of cases according to the literature [6]. Shoulder joint pain is the third most frequently identified among all musculoskeletal problems, second only to lumbar spine and knee pain [9].

Rotator cuff injury is more common, accounting for up to 86% of cases, and is the most common cause of disability [6,10].

According to the literature, 30 to 50% of rotator cuff tears cause pain syndrome, while other tears have no clinical signs [16]. Out of these patients, only 20% of patients visit medical institutions and undergo examination, others go to chiropractors, chiropractors, and self-administer analgesic medications [15].

Instability of the shoulder joint in athletes. A classic shoulder injury in young athletes is instability of the shoulder joint [4]. It is important therapeutically for athletes to differentiate the various forms of instability and to differentiate from hyperlaxity. In addition to macrotraumatic shoulder instability, which usually occurs as a result of an initial adequate dislocation, it is necessary to distinguish between a group of shoulder complaints associated with hyperlaxity and a group of microtraumatic shoulder instability. Jobe et al. (1989) developed a classification of shoulder pathology in athletes of the shoulder joint, which distinguishes between pure primary impingement, secondary impingement due to instability or hyperlaxity and pure instability in four groups [2,7,8].

Differentiating hyperweakness from instability is extremely important in any therapeutic approach. By definition, laxity describes the physiological translation of a joint and has no pathological significance, whereas hyperlaxity is the ability to translate that increases above the physiological level with accompanying clinical symptoms. Instability refers to the inability of the shoulder joint to center the head of the joint in the glenoid cavity under load. Subluxation is an increased pathological displacement under load without complete loss of contact between the head of the joint and the socket. When the load causing the subluxation is relieved, spontaneous reduction occurs. Dislocation is a complete loss of contact of the articular surfaces, requiring reduction to restore [3,9].

Microtraumatic imbalance of the shoulder. Sports activities put a significant burden on the shoulder joint. It can lead to microtraumatisation with a change in the sequence of movements and initially asymptomatic pathology. This means that the shoulder can no longer properly coordinate the sequence of movements during movement and morphological changes occur with injuries to the bony, active and passive stabilizers of the shoulder. Timely recognition and treatment of this overload is an important key to preventing damage or arthroscopic treatment according to the pathology [3,6,7]. There are 4 different theoretical models explaining the etiology and pathogenesis of microtraumatic instability in athletes [6]. Jobe model. According to it, an extremely large range of motion and repeated acceleration and deceleration forces cause damage to the muscles, capsules and ligaments. The anterior structures of the shoulder are primarily affected, leading to capsule widening followed by subluxation. This leads to capsule shortening and eventually impingement. In this form of instability, the lesion of the RUJ is very often detected as a secondary rupture of the posterior glenoid with fibrillation of the posterior glenoid surface.

Model ASI. This model has not been widely used in the assessment of shoulder pain in athletes. During the pull-up phase with internal rotation and abduction, anterior displacement of the humeral head may occur with subsequent entrapment of the subscapularis tendon by the lesser

tubercle at the anterior border of the glenoid muscle and injury to the cranial subscapularis tendon and anterior labrum.

The Burkhart-Morgan model. It occurs as a pathological mechanism of capsular contracture with a subsequent decrease in internal rotation during abduction in the shoulder joint, the so-called "girdle internal rotation deficiency" (GIRD). This leads to a posterior-upward displacement of the contact point of the humeral head in the glenoid cavity, which leads to increased external rotation. Labral injury may result from excessive external rotation due to increased shear forces. Similar to the Jobe model, secondary rotator cuff changes may occur on the glenoid side due to shear and rotation forces.

Kibler model. The Kibler model suggests that scapular displacement is the cause of shoulder pain in athletes. The reason is the resulting muscular imbalance, leading to structural changes in the acromioclavicular or glenohumeral joint.

Macrotraumatic shoulder instability. Shoulder instability is considered a classic sports injury in athletes; in 70% of cases, dislocation occurs as a sports injury [1,2]. According to the literature, traumatic shoulder dislocation occurs in the anteroinferior direction in 95-97% [5,7]. The mechanism of anterior shoulder dislocation is in most cases due to the force of abduction with an external rotation component of the shoulder [11]:

1. The athlete falls and lands on an outstretched, abducted and externally rotated arm. The landing reinforces this posture and causes the humeral head to dislocate from the socket.

2. The athlete attempts to stop or block the opponent by extending the arm outward, abducted, and externally rotated. As a result, if the opponent hits the arm with his weight in this position, the head of the humerus is pulled out of the socket.

3. Dislocation can also occur due to a direct force that pushes the humeral head forward.

4. A special form of anterior traumatic shoulder dislocation is the "straightened dislocation", in which the humeral head is forced out of the socket during a hyperabduction movement due to a blow to the acromion. The affected arm is then elastically fixed in an abduction position of 110 to 160 [3,12].

Classifications of Shoulder Instability. In order to better differentiate the various forms of instability and specific treatment regimens, various classifications have been established in everyday clinical and scientific practice. They depend to varying degrees on the etiology, direction, degree, time, frequency, and arbitrary behavior of the tendency to dislocation. Due to the often mixed forms of shoulder instability combined with a hyperlaxity component, there are many classifications [2,15].

Classification of atraumatic and traumatic instability according to Matsen. The classification initially separates atraumatic and traumatic shoulder instability [2,4,9]. Accordingly, atraumatic shoulder instability should be assessed as a symptom complex, which is summarized by the abbreviation "AMBRI": atraumatic (A), multidirectional (M), bilateral (B), conservative rehabilitation therapy (R). If conservative therapy is unsuccessful, surgical intervention may be indicated.

Classification of shoulder instability according to Warner. Etiologically, this classification distinguishes between macrotraumatic, microtraumatic and atraumatic, voluntary and involuntary, as well as congenital and neuromuscular types of shoulder instability. The degree of instability is classified by dislocation, subluxation and increased translation. The direction of instability (anterior, posterior, inferior, superior) is also assessed. Matsen's classification is supplemented by the frequency of dislocations (acute, recurrent, chronic/intertwined) [14].

Bayley's classification of shoulder instability. The classification is based on the distinction between traumatic and atraumatic origin. In addition, muscle imbalance is considered as a third etiopathological factor, since positional instability can occur due to impaired innervation of the shoulder and shoulder girdle muscles. Based on the knowledge of existing mixed forms, Bayley identifies three etiopathological cornerstones (polar groups from I to III), the axes of which represent mixed forms [4]. The weakness of this classification is that it does not take into account all mixed forms with hyperlaxity components. Almost a third of patients with unstable shoulder have this in combination with multidirectional hyperlaxity [6].

Gerber and Nyffeler classification of shoulder instability. The classification includes mixed forms and different patterns of injury. It distinguishes between static (class A) and dynamic instability (class B), as well as voluntary dislocation (class C). Class A (static instability) includes superior, anterior, inferior, or posterior decentration of the humeral head due to rotator cuff defects, degenerative, or atraumatic diseases. Class C (voluntary dislocation) is an independent clinical picture that should not really be considered instability [3].

Pathology of macrotraumatic instability of the shoulder joint. The defeat of Bankart. The classic Bankart lesion describes a disruption of the integrity of the transition zone between the socket cartilage and the labrum when the glenohumeral ligament is intact [7]. The double labral lesion represents a continuation of the Bankart lesion, in addition to the complete separation of the labrum from the edge of the articular process, there is separation of the intact attachment of the inferior glenohumeral ligament to the limbus; this means a double detachment of the labrum, both from the glenoid rim and from the intact inferior glenohumeral ligament [4,9]. Perthes and ALPSA lesion. The classic Perthes lesion is a fresh complete avulsion of the labrum from the edge of the limbus, which forms a so-called periosteal pocket. A chronic cicatricial Perthes lesion is called an ALPSA lesion [2]. Here, the displaced capsular-labral-ligamentous complex forms a cicatricial bulge anterior to the neck of the scapula at the bottom of the torn periosteal pocket. A special form is a triple lesion with additional separation of the labrum from the dissected inferior glenohumeral ligament-capsule complex. Especially with recurrent dislocations, the incidence of injuries to the middle glenohumeral ligament and inferior glenohumeral ligament [3], as well as the anterior inferior capsule-labrum complex [90], increases significantly. An MRI examination revealed that the anteroinferior capsular-ligament complex expands by an average of 19% after repeated shoulder dislocations [3,6,7].

A GLAD lesion is a tear of the anteroinferior labrum with damage to the adjacent cartilage, and articular cartilage damage may also occur.

A HAGL lesion is an avulsion of the joint capsule from the humerus [6]. Both the middle glenohumeral ligament and/or the inferior glenohumeral ligament are torn or torn at their insertion into the humerus, rarely in association with a subscapularis tendon injury.

SLAP lesion. A common lesion associated with instability (up to 10%) is injury to the insertion of the biceps tendon of the superior labrum [6,8].

In 1990, Snyder was the first to describe so-called SLAP lesions (“superior labral avulsion of the shoulder joint associated with the tendon of the long head of the biceps”) and classified them into 4 types depending on the extent of the lesion [9]. In 1995, Maffet expanded this definition to include types 5 through 7, describing pathology extending beyond the labrum-biceps tendon-ligament complex [5]. SLAP-2 lesions were further divided by Burkhart and Morgan into anterior (SLAP-2a), posterior (SLAP-2b) and combined forms of injury (SLAP-2c) [5]. In particular, the cause of SLAP-2a in athletes has been described as hypovascularization of the anterosuperior lip and is called “Andrews' lesion”, first described in 1985 [3]. Bone lesions of macrotraumatic instability. In the context of anterior shoulder dislocation, special attention should be paid to bony lesions of the glenoid cavity (Bankart lesion) and impression fractures of the humeral head (Hill-Sachs lesion), the diagnosis of which, including evaluation and treatment, contribute significantly to the success of shoulder stabilization [1,3].

Hill-Sachs injury. It is an impacted (impression) fracture of the head of the humerus). The incidence ranges from 47% after initial dislocation to 100% with recurrent instability and affects up to 25% of cases of subluxation [4].

Bone Bankart lesion. The bone defect of the anterior inferior rim of the acetabulum can be considered as a shear fracture caused by dislocation or subluxation, and its frequency is 22% in first dislocations and up to 73% in recurrent dislocations [3]. It has been experimentally proven that refixation of the labral ligament complex directly in the area of the Bankart fracture defect leads to a significant loss of external rotation, with the loss of external rotation being 25° per cm of the bone defect distance. In a biomechanical study on a cadaver, the authors also show using glenoid osteotomy that with defect sizes exceeding 21% of the glenoid length, Bankart reconstruction alone without bone reconstruction does not provide sufficient stability. In particular, differentiation of articular bone

damage into "fracture type" and "erosion type" is of fundamental importance for the choice of surgical procedure [28,79].

The formation of rotator cuff injuries of the shoulder joint in physically active patients is associated with many factors, including the type of activity, mechanism of injury, and the presence of various symptoms. An important feature of this group of patients is the asymptomatic course of most shoulder injuries [1,3]. In athletes, an important criterion of rehabilitation effectiveness is the frequency and speed of return to the previous level of sports activity. According to many studies, more than 50% of patients after surgical treatment cannot return to their previous level of activity [3].

Ruptures on the articular surface side are common in throwing sports athletes, and on the subacromial surface side in bodybuilders or people engaged in vigorous physical labour [13]. The duration of conservative treatment varies depending on the severity of symptoms, concomitant pathology and individual characteristics. Up to 40% of patients are unresponsive to conservative treatment [14]. Surgical treatment is indicated for athletes in whom conservative treatment has been ineffective. The results of arthroscopic debridement among athletes are highly variable. Arthroscopic debridement and subacromial decompression in athletes under 40 years of age resulted in 86% satisfactory results in the group with traumatic mechanism and 66% in the group with atraumatic injury, with 4% of patients in the former group and 45% in the latter group [15]. Diagnostic and endoscopic equipment with high sensitivity, minimally invasive surgical treatments, and improved outcomes for patients with shoulder rotator cuff injuries have all been made possible by recent scientific and technological advancements in medicine. However, there is currently no rehabilitation algorithm that aims to fully restore labor capacity in patients who have been injured in the shoulder rotator cuff. It should be noted that athletes must restore the ability to bear significant physical loads in addition to restoring labor and domestic skills. These physical loads place a high demand on joint stability, mobility, muscle strength, endurance, speed, and strength qualities. The athlete's ability to return to training will be determined by the balanced and differentiated application of recovery means over various periods of physical rehabilitation, each of which is appropriate for the patient's functional state.

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9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

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